

The Nador west med port complex serving the territorial attractiveness of the eastern region: Qualitative study

Tarek Lakhroufi, (PhD Student)

*Laboratory of International Economics and Economic Development
Faculty of Legal, Economic and Social Sciences Ain-Chok
Hassan II University, Casablanca, Morocco*

Brahim El Majidi, (PhD Student)

*Laboratory of Research in Territorial, Integrated and Functional Management
National School of Business and Management
Mohamed Premier University, Oujda, Morocco*

Correspondence address:

National School of Business and Management
Address : University complex BP 658 Oujda
Mohamed Premier University
Morocco (Oujda)
Téléphone : +212536506989 Fax +212536506984
lakhroufi_tarek@hotmail.fr

Disclosure statement:

Authors are not aware of any findings that might be perceived as affecting the objectivity of this study

Conflicts of interest:

The author reports no conflicts of interest.

Cite this article

Lakhroufi, T., & El Majidi, B. (2021). The Nador west med port complex serving the territorial attractiveness of the eastern region: : Qualitative study. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance, Auditing, Management and Economics*, 2(1), 330-343. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4474459>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4474459

Published online: January 29, 2021

Copyright © 2021 – IJAFAME

The Nador west med port complex serving the territorial attractiveness of the eastern region: Qualitative study

Abstract

This article tries to assess the influence of the Nador west med (NWM) port complex on the territorial attractiveness of the eastern region in a context marked by the implementation of the Royal initiative for the development of the Eastern Region (2003), the implementation of the policy of large building sites and the territorialization of sectoral strategies. The achievement of this objective led us to use qualitative tools, notably the interview guide. The sample of this study has confirmed the favourable impact of this port complex on the territorial attractiveness of the region, while highlighting the conditions related in particular to fiscal advantages, to the formalization of the informal sector and to the promotion of the territorial offer. This trial took place in a pandemic situation (COVID19) negatively affecting the duration of the interviews with the interviewees.

Keywords: Territorial Attractiveness, Seaport, NWM, Eastern Region

JEL Classification : R 11, H 54, O 18

Paper type: Empirical research

Résumé

Cet article essaie d'évaluer l'influence de complexe portuaire Nador west med (NWM) sur l'attractivité territoriale de la région de l'oriental dans un contexte marqué par l'implémentation de l'initiative royale du développement de l'oriental (2003), de la mise en œuvre de la politique de grands chantiers et de la territorialisation des stratégies sectorielles. L'aboutissement de cet objectif nous a conduit à faire recours aux outils qualitatifs notamment le guide d'entretien. L'échantillon de cette étude a confirmé l'impact favorable de ce complexe portuaire sur l'attractivité territoriale de la région, tout en mettant en avant des conditions liées notamment aux avantages fiscaux, à la formalisation de l'informel, à la promotion de l'offre territoriale. Cet essai s'est déroulé dans une situation pandémique (COVID19) affectant négativement la durée des entretiens avec les interviewés.

Mots-clés : Attractivité territoriale, Port maritime, NWM, région de l'Oriental

Classification JEL : R 11, H 54, O 18

Type de l'article : Recherche appliquée

Introduction

Over the last two decades, the Kingdom has made colossal efforts provide Morocco with the logistics infrastructure necessary for its economic development, through the launch of the policy of major construction sites which consists in providing the regions of Morocco with the physical capital necessary for its development and the implementation of a series of sectoral policies to improve the sectors relating to world trades.

In this sense, the port infrastructure constitutes a major element of the logistics infrastructure which for a long time played a very important role in the economic development of the maritime countries of the world (Park & Seo, 2016). Morocco is no exception to this observation; it has undertaken colossal efforts to improve the performance of its seaports so that they may be a locomotive of the Moroccan economy (Lakhroufi & Moussamir, 2020), but also to make them a better means of access to international markets. Indeed, this infrastructure generates a series of positive effects such as the multiplier effect, the diffusion effect, the competitiveness effect, contributing to improving the attractiveness of the hinterland of the seaports and consequently increasing the territorial attractiveness of the Kingdom's regions (El Majidi & Lakhroufi, 2017). In this respect, the variable of territorial attractiveness occupies an important place in academic debates in general and in research related to territorial dynamics in particular. The concept of attractiveness has taken an important and strategic place for all those interested in territories, the economy, the social, the evolution of societies, from local to global. One of the major objectives of policies for attractiveness is to push investment activity in order to catch up with the gap that exists in terms of employment and infrastructure.

The elements of territorial attractiveness are multiple and diverse. Recently, port infrastructure is positioned as a better element of this attractiveness, especially in the case of maritime regions. In fact, the Eastern Region, which in the last decade has been part of a gradual reform process and of a new path of economic development and consolidation, enjoys a set of elements of territorial attractiveness, especially those related to human capital, physical capital, market size and institutional stability.

In this paper, we focus on physical capital and more precisely on the Nador west med (NWM) port complex since it is, first of all, an important port logistics infrastructure, it is a new industrial-port project that will reconfigure the economic face of the Oriental region and it will be built on the strategic site of Betoia Bay, located on the western side of the Cape of Three Forks, less than 250 miles from the Strait of Gibraltar, opposite the main East-West shipping routes for containers and petroleum product traffic (UNCTAD, 2011). The objective of this document is to assess the effects of Nador West Med on the territorial attractiveness of the Oriental region by using a semi-directive maintenance guide targeting the main public and private actors of the Oriental region.

1. The theoretical framework

1.1. Historical evolution of seaports

Seaports have long played a strategic role in the achievement of a series of public policies and in facilitating access to private actors in international markets. Topics related to seaports have taken an important place in modern literature, which has aroused the interest of researchers has studied the concept of a seaport from different angles. Indeed, this concept is used in several fields including economics, geography, engineering, logistics, ecology, urban planning....

Historically, the concept of the seaport has gone through 5 essential stages UNCTAD (1994). The first stage, ports were simple interfaces between the land and the sea allowing the transport of goods by the traditional operations of loading and unloading of goods. The

second stage, the port is considered as a center of services in the sector of transport, industry and commerce that offers services through logistics tools.

In the third step, the port has experienced considerable development with the explosion of the phenomenon of containerization and multimodality. It becomes a dynamic variable in the international system of production and distribution. The fourth step, ports are becoming systems connecting many port areas. In other words, the seaport integrated international supply chains by providing cell-wide services to several generators logistics s in different geographical areas. The last step, ports focus on the port community, through market mechanisms, incentives and government policies for users and port operators. This last step is based on the concept of community and relationships with stakeholders, since ports should be able to solve community problems in a structured and sustainable way.

Conceptually, the economists Goss, R. (1990) Bauchet (1992), Goss, R. (2002), Culinane K. & Wayne K. Telley (2006), treated the concept of the seaport in its economic framework. The port is a complex system based on tangible and intangible elements, intended for the service of ships and goods.

Similarly, it is an operating system that solves inefficiency constraints and finds solutions for optimizing operations directly related to ports, especially those of handling and those indirectly related to ports such as logistics operations. In this sense, the port market is composed of an offer based on capital, labor, production, energy, congestion, speed and costs ...and a demand based on: weight, speed, distance, reliability, safety.

For geographers Rodrigue, J.P. (1994), Fischer, A (1963) Jackson G. (1983), Vigarié (1993) and Bired. J, (1971), the port is a contact zone between two spaces organized for the transport of goods and passengers. These two spaces are terrestrial and maritime. The port being a third one ensuring the organized transition for the traffic..

In another way, it is a contact space between the two areas, land traffic and maritime traffic, its role is to ensure a solution of continuity between two transport schemes adapted to the crossing of two spaces with different characteristics. For researchers in this field, it focuses more on the specificity of the place and marginalizes the specificities linked to port functions.

The advances made in the field of logistics have influenced seaports in a positive way, making them a strategic variable in the various trade negotiations and policies of the countries. Thus, seaports are not mere transport infrastructure, but developed logistics center's capable of driving up economic development and shifting the balance of power.

1.2. Territory

Etymologically, probably from Latin territorium "land around a town, domain, district," from terra "earth, land" (from PIE root *ters- "to dry") + -orium, suffix denoting place (see -ory). Sense of "any tract of land, district, region" is first attested c. 1600. Specific U.S. sense of "organized self-governing region not yet a state" is from 1799. Regions defended by animals from 1774 (Sucháček, J , 2008).

According to Lajarge, R. (2000), Prax. J. (2002), Bertacchini.Y (2002) the territory is not a neutral object decided in abstractions and disconnected from reality. Above all, it is cobbled together by the players based on a large number of constantly changing parameters. This definition shows that the territory is a socio-spatial entity where there are two primordial notions : the first refers to the space and the other to the actors who act on this space. This double entry to the concept of territory is very explicit in the definition of Di Méo G. (1999) for him the territory testifies to an appropriation at the same time economic, ideological and political of the space by groups which give themselves a particular representation of themselves, of their history, of their singularity. Méo affirms that the groups living in a

territory have an identity which distinguishes them from groups in other territories, this is what we will try to detail when speaking of territorial identity.

For Colletis, G. & Rychen, F. (2004), The European Observatory LEADER (1999), when dealing with the notion of territory, we approach three dimensions, namely:

- The territorial entity which takes up the definition of geographical space.
- The physical analysis which is interested in the elements which appear in the territory and which contribute to the realization of the activities by the individuals or the groups of individuals who live there.

The notion of governance which encompasses the different vertical and horizontal coordination between the actors of a territory includes the decision-making process.

Finally, we can conclude that the territory:

"Is a space of interaction between activities and social groups, and it is its interactions that give it its identity and that differentiates it from other spaces ; the notion of the territory in its most complete acceptance encompasses at the same time the resources, the living environment, the activities, the actors, their interrelationships, the awareness that they belong to the same development entity"

Territorial attractiveness: a look at several visions.

Territories put themselves under the imperative of being aware of the upheaval in the economy and in world politics. However, an attractive territory will not always be attractive if it remains inert (Hatem & Py (2008), Coeuré & Rabaut (2003)). On the other hand, a competitive territory is defined by its quality and its lasting attractiveness (Malecki (2004), Harvey (1989)). To this end, attractiveness can be defined as the capacity of a geographic area to attract people and skills and to create businesses while offering these actors the optimal conditions for locating themselves in this geographic space. According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2005), attractiveness is defined as "the capacity to attract a qualified workforce and skills as a means of promoting economic development and urban regeneration". In addition, "attractiveness is the capacity of a territory to offer actors the conditions that persuade them to locate their projects on their territory rather than on another" (Hatem, 2004). The attractiveness of the territory comprises seven elements.

Figure 1 : The elements of attractiveness of the territory

Source: Francis & Régis (2009)

Moreover, the attractiveness of the territory is measured according to its nature and the number of hotel occupations and passengers entering stations and airports. A tourist territory is considered as an example, the brightness and the number of cultural and festive events evaluate a cultural territory.

1.3. Territorial Attractiveness and Seaports

The logistics infrastructure is among the essential factors of territorial attractiveness. Indeed, the logistics infrastructure is an essential element of territorial attractiveness. It ensures its accessibility, which improves territorial competitiveness. The interaction between territorial attractiveness and logistics infrastructure can be examined on several fronts. Accessibility which is a fundamental component is also a specific place linked to a point of interest in a reference space or territory (Rietveld & Bruinsma, 1998).

This is the framework for the seaport, which has become an extremely important logistical infrastructure for the success of a territory since it constitutes a connection link with the international scene. It is rare when we find seaports in an isolated territory, they have been established in territories where there are other logistical infrastructure such as industrial zones, commercial zones making the port a variable of attractiveness of investments and therefore the attractive territory Rietveld, P. (1989)

Figure 2 : The nature of the effects generated by the relationship : Territorial attractiveness / Sea ports

Source : Authors

The relationship between territorial attractiveness and seaports generally translates into a series of effects that make this combination an important equation in the emergence of regions. Indeed, this relationship does not date back to yesterday, but its nature has taken many forms and angles, and each researcher deals with this issue from his or her own perspective. The diagram below shows the nature of the effects generated by this relationship:

- **Centralization effect:** the seaport leads to the emergence of logistics zones in its hinterland, which makes its territory attractive and open to any possibility of extension and development. For Duranton & Puga (2005), having a highly developed logistics infrastructure will make it possible to attract companies, leading to a concentration of companies, which improves the attractiveness of the region. This concentration builds a system of cooperation between a set of companies, called the competitiveness cluster. Zheng, S. & Negenborn, R.R. (2014).

- Multiplied effect: the development of seaports encourages entrepreneurs to invest in port areas and in areas adjacent to seaports, thus providing the territory with a set of economic advantages.
- Diffusion effect: the added value created by seaports is not limited to its area, but influences its micro-environment and macro-environment, thus affecting the territory in a positive way.
- The complementarity effect: the performance of seaports and the territory's endowments are complementary and they offer private operators an attractive territory capable of responding to import and export issues. (M. Jason & al 2016).
- Competitiveness effect: the layout of a high-performance seaport and an attractive territory capable of raising the level of competitiveness and it becomes an important motto in any public policy wishing economic development. (Haezendonck, Elvira and al. 2000), (OECD, 2011).

2. Empirical framework

2.1. The presentation of the industrial-port complex: Nador West Med (NWM)

In countries where geographic position is a competitive advantage and gradual liberalization is adopted in its foreign policy. Seaports occupy a strategic place in the economy of these countries. Morocco is aware of the strategic role of seaports in the success of its various actions aimed at a more comprehensive development of its economy. The kingdom's ports are based on natural endowments, particularly its geographical position which is characterized by a coastal line of about 2 200 km, developing on two Atlantic and Mediterranean sea fronts, and built endowments such as the implementation of the policy of major construction sites, the port reform (2006), the national strategy for the development of logistics competitiveness (SNDCL) and the national port strategy by 2030.

The NWM project is in line with the policies of the major construction sites which consists in providing Morocco with the port infrastructure necessary for its economic development and to meet the various challenges raised by its policy of economic openness and its desire to be a port hub on the Mediterranean Basin. Similarly, it represents a structuring economic development tool that is part of an integrated territorial development project, associating both port infrastructure and business parks (NWM 2014).

The port infrastructure related to the NWM project consists in offering a development potential in the medium and long term allowing potential operators and shipowners to build visions and perspectives, a progressive realization of the infrastructure and flexibility in planning possible future extensions and a capacity to adapt to changes in traffic and shipping industries. They are designed and studied to be realized in several modules (NWM, 2017).

Thus, this project is backed by the realization of the motorway link with the new Nador West Med Port at a cost of 4.5 billion dirhams (MMDH), the rail network will be extended through the continuation of the realization of connectivity projects rail from the ports of Nador West Med (MAD 3 billion). In terms of governance, a public company Nador West Med was created and charged with the realization, development, planning, promotion and management of the said project. (BERD, 2015)

2.2. The Oriental Region Profile

After having exposed the NWM port complex, it is appropriate to present the Eastern Region, since it constitutes, next to the port in question, a primordial variable. In fact, in order to analyse this region properly, we use the SWOT strategic analysis method, focusing on the elements related to the physical capital.

✓ Strengths

- A strategic geographical location between the desert and the Mediterranean, between Algeria and the rest of Morocco; and beyond, it opens up to the whole of the Maghreb and southern Europe (Euro-Mediterranean and Euro-Maghreb crossroads).
 - The region offers direct and rapid access to the French, Spanish and Algerian markets, at ultra-competitive costs. Indeed, the Eastern Region is the part closest to Valencia, Barcelona, Marseille and Genoa, which are important growth poles in the Western Mediterranean Basin and which will be part of the same economic unit in 2011, after the full force of association agreements with the European Union Ali (Kharroubi (2009)).
 - A Mediterranean seafront extending from the mouth of *Nekor* in the west to that of the *Kiss* in the east, over more than 200 km, allowing the development of economic activities related to different sectors (fishing, seaside tourism, maritime transport ...) (Oujda Chamber of Commerce, Industry and Services (2016))
- ✓ **Weaknesses**
- A gap between supply and demand in terms of the qualifications of the workforce (UMP (2015)).
 - A disabling financial situation and a lack of visibility on the land potentially available for the reception of investment projects.
 - A concentrated investment at the level of large urban agglomerations generating strong disparities in the urban environment and between the urban and the rural.
- ✓ **Opportunities**
- A Royal initiative for the development of the region, carrying a new regional development strategy, focused on an innovative vision broader than Maghreb, both Euro-Mediterranean and Saharan, aiming for a modern and competitive regional economy.
 - Existence of several agreements at the international level: association agreement with the European Union (2012), free trade agreements with Turkey and in several countries of the Arab world and the Agadir agreement.
 - Existence of several development poles under construction from North to South of the Region: port and maritime-industrial pole in the Province of Nador, tourists pole in Saidaia, in the Province of Berkane, agro-industrial pole in Berkane, university pole oriented on the knowledge economy and new technologies in Oujda, a pole of reconversion of the mining economy (in decline in the South of the Region in Jerada, Bouarfa and Figuig) reoriented on the oasis economy, niche tourism, breeding and promotion of local products, transport logistics center in Taourirt (Ministry of Tourism (2020)).
 - A pole of attraction par excellence for investments, particularly in real estate, trade and services thanks to the basic infrastructure projects (ring road, railroad, port, etc.) launched by the State as well as major tourist projects in progress by foreign groups and thanks in particular to the existing desire to renew the regional economic base and the sources of income for the Oriental (HCP, 2017)
- ✓ **Threat**
- Significant financial savings thanks in particular to cash transfers from MRE. However, this capital deposited in the cities of the region, in particular in Oujda and Nador, is underused for productive investment purposes.
 - Complexity and redundancy of interventions at the local level, diversity of development projects and diversity of actors involved).
 - The geopolitical vicissitudes since the independence of Algeria in 1962, depending on the climate which prevails on bilateral relations, the Moroccan-Algerian border has

experienced cycles of closures-openings totaling over 45 years more than 25 years of closure: in 1963, 1975 to 1988 and 1994 to present.

3. Research method

3.1. Research design and hypotheses of study

This work plans to study the effect of the NWM project on the territorial attractiveness of the Oriental region, through semi-directive interview guides for the main stakeholders of the Oriental region. The choice of the qualitative tool is justified by the absence of data on the variables that represent the variables studied to conduct a quantitative study. The elaboration of the said study is based on the hypothetico-deductive approach which relies on hypothetical propositions to deduce logical consequences Thiétart & Coll (2003). This paper therefore attempts to test the following hypotheses:

H1: The Oriental region is an irresistible prediction to attract investors

H2 : The NWM project will strengthen the maritime presence of the Oriental region

H3 : The NWM project will arouse the interest of private actors to invest in the eastern region

H4 : The NWM project will positively influence the attractiveness of the Oriental region

3.2. Sample selection and description

The verification of these hypotheses requires the selection of a sample capable of answering our questions which are part of a purely and practical order. The list below shows the qualities of the interviewees:

- The president of the municipal council of Nador and in Driouch
- The president of the provincial council of the province of Oujda, Nador and Driouch
- The President of the Oriental Chamber of Commerce, Industry and Services
- The rapporteur of the president of the chamber of commerce, industry and services of the Oriental
- The director of Bank al Maghreb in Oujda and in Nador
- The director of the national agency for the promotion of employment and skills (ANAPEC) Oujda and in Nador
- The provincial delegate of METLE of Nador
- the port community (Customs, The national port agency, Freight forwarders, Marsamaroc, Importers / Exporters and Insurers)
- The banks
- Representatives of civil society associations

It should be noted that this interview guide is developed remotely through the Google Meet platform, as well as in some cases we have used telephone calls and emails, in order to collect the interview guide responses, ensuring strict compliance preventive and health rules laid down by health authorities against COVID-19.

4. Results and discussion

In this axis, we present the analyzes concerning the contribution of the NWM project in boosting the territorial attractiveness of the Eastern Region:

Does the eastern region have the assets to attract investment?

Local actors claim that the Eastern Region has all the ingredients to host major investment projects and these assets are presented in two categories namely:

- Tangible capital: a surface area (88,681 km²) equivalent to that of Austria or South Korea, situated at the crossroads of the Maghreb and Europe on a 200 km seafront on the Mediterranean. Similarly, it is boosted by the launch and implementation of

major infrastructure projects (railways, seaways, roads, etc.) and tourism projects (Saïdia, Marchica, etc.).

- **Intangible capital:** the region has more than 2 million inhabitants (6.4% of Morocco's population), 57% of whom are under 25 years old, constituting an advantageous labor force in terms of cost compared with Europe. In addition, young people in the region benefit from a diversified education offered by the various higher education and vocational training institutions.

Name the infrastructure that makes the oriental an irresistible predilection for attracting investment?

For the local actors, the flagship projects making the Eastern Region attractive for investment are distributed as follows:

- **The Air Mode:** there are two flagship projects namely:
 - **Oujda-Angad International Airport:** It is located in the North-East of Morocco. It is one of those rare pearls that constitute the new generation of airports built by ONDA.
 - **Nador Al Aroui Airport:** is equipped with a terminal and a runway covering 8,100 m², as well as two car parks for aircraft and a meteorological station.
- **The Seaport mode:** the region has three main ports:
 - **Port of Beni Ansar:** is next to the port of Melilla from which it is only separated by a narrow jetty that can accommodate 200-metre-long ships.
 - **Saïdia Marina:** Marina Saïdia A new milestone for the socio-economic and tourist development of the eastern region.
 - **The Nador West Med Port:** is a future Moroccan oil transshipment port which will be built in Betoya Bay. This port will be larger than the port of Tangier Med.
- **The road mode:** is mainly composed by:
 - **Mediterranean Ring Road:** The National Road 16 or Mediterranean Ring Road or Rif Ring Road is a Moroccan national road which links the whole Rif region.
 - **Fez-Oujda motorway line**
 - **Guerif-port NWM motorway line** (under construction, 104 km)
- **The rail transports**
 - **Railway line Nador-Taourirt** (117 km).
- **The logistic mode:**
 - **The technopole of Oujda :** is a project relating to a pole of activities near the airport of Oujda Angad (12 km from Oujda) on the territory of the rural commune of Ahl Angad. It is composed of four distinct plots, 25000 direct jobs.
 - **Selouane Industrial Zone:** The Selouane Industrial Park (IP) provides investors operating in the industrial sector with a suitable environment for carrying out their projects, with quality infrastructure and optimal connectivity to the city of Nador.

How qualify the impact of NWM harbor on regional economic development? Do you have any forecasts?

The interviewees confirmed the important role of the port of Nador west med in the economic development of the region, the strengthening of the port offer of the eastern region and the contribution to the fight against regional disparities.

Indeed, the employment variable occupied a primordial place in their answers since the Eastern region suffers from a high unemployment rate compared to the regions of the kingdom. This project will generate jobs in particular through activities directly linked to port trades such as the Port Authority and other administrations, Services linked to ships, cargo services, related port services (maritime agencies, refueling, security, storage ...). Indirect activities which make use of port infrastructure and the port hinterland where economic wealth is concentrated thanks to the presence of numerous activity sectors, in other words,

jobs created by the needs of the industrial and logistical activities installed and by transport goods and induced activities created by current consumption needs of activities linked to ports in a direct and indirect way.

In terms of forecasts, local actors estimated the creation of more than 5,000 direct jobs and more than 100,000 indirect jobs. Thus, this project will constitute an unprecedented solution for the issues related to the spread of informal trades in the region, particularly those relating to smuggling.

Do you think that the NWM port will have a remarkable effect on the territorial attractiveness of the Oriental?

The interviewees insisted on the success of the port Nador west med (NWM) in order to improve the territorial attractiveness of the east since it will be the only economic catalyst of the said region in a context where the region suffers from a lack of structuring projects capable of advancing in the field of regional competitiveness. The industrial-port project Nador West Med can contribute to the improvement of the territorial attractiveness by :

- Erecting Nador as a 2 Mediterranean port epôle

Morocco has been able to improve its Mediterranean maritime presence by creating the Tangier med port complex. Indeed, since the operationalization of the Tangier Med Port, a remarkable evolution has been welcomed by all international organizations in this field. Moreover, this increase has been crowned by an improvement in the ranking of the maritime connectivity index developed by UNCTAD. Interviewees have always taken as a basic example the said port to justify the success of the Tangier Med Port, which will, for them, certainly strengthen Moroccan Port activities and lead to a series of positive effects in the eastern region.

- Fostering the emergence of a diversified economic fabric

The NWM project's main objective is the creation of an industrial port capable of putting the region on the road to development. This project is surrounded by a hinterland composed of a series of companies specialized in the fields of transport, logistics, energy, services ... In other words, the project will ensure the concentration of investment in projects that generate growth, employment and innovation. This will create a synergy between the port and the industrial sector of the region.

- More promotion (Territorial Marketing)

Territorial marketing is a global approach to work on regional attractiveness on a geographical scale ranging from local to global. The Oriental border region has suffered in the past, it must now draw future prospects, several local actors, including the DG of the Oriental Development Agency, have stressed the cruel lack of marketing and promotion of the region's assets, both nationally and internationally. For the regional leaders (private and public), the NWM project can make the Oriental a commercial brand that will enhance its potential, and will allow it to benefit from an increased notoriety especially in terms of accessibility and contact with the outside world.

- Giving a tax advantage to the Region

The interviewees insisted on the role of the free zone in the attractiveness of investments since it will offer important tax advantages in order to improve the attractiveness of the port in a particular way and the attractiveness of the region in general. According to the President CCIS of the Eastern CCIS said zone, which covers an area of 4,978 ha, is part of the Integrated Industrial Platforms Program and could accommodate all non-polluting industrial activities and all services related to port activities.

- Reducing the weight of informality

All the interviewees stressed the important role of the project in reducing the weight of the informal sector in a context where it is the source of income for a large proportion of households in the East. Indeed, the agricultural labor force is moving towards more lucrative

smuggling activities, leading to the absence of product traceability, disastrous transport and storage conditions, and the loss of tax revenue. According to the head of the economic division at the prefecture of Nador, the informal sector generates a turnover estimated at 6 billion Dh, or 40% of the 15 billion Dh national, equivalent to the turnover made by 1 200 SMEs / SMIs combined and consequently 32 400 jobs lost.

5. Summary and Conclusions

The experience of the Tangier Med Port complex has been able to strengthen Morocco's maritime presence on the international port scene, but it has also made the Northern Region a locomotive of the national economy by attracting a series of international companies to set up in the hinterland of this port, which has contributed to the massive creation of employment. This success reinforces the chances of success of the Nador west med (NWM) complex so that it is a better tool for the territorial attractiveness of the Oriental region.

Indeed, this present work has been able to confirm, through the interview guide, the hypotheses put forward regarding the favourable impact of the NWM industrial-port complex on the territorial attractiveness of the Oriental region. Precisely enough the interviewees confirmed the strategic role of this seaport in improving the territorial attractiveness of the Oriental region, since it will not be a simple creation of infrastructure, but the creation of an integrated port logistics platform that will put the region in the global value chains, which will lead to a series of economic effects relating to job creation, the establishment of good practices of entrepreneurship, the promotion of local enterprise, the improvement of the territorial attractiveness of the region at national and international level. Similarly, the interviewees insisted on the capacities of the Oriental region to support this huge project in terms of diversified human capital, competitiveness clusters, related transport infrastructure (road, rail and air).

In another way, this project will give concrete expression to the desired balance and comfort the Oriental region in its quest for economic attractiveness by providing it with adequate means to successfully convert it into an attractive area to strong potential and investment opportunities.

One of the limitations of our study is that we examined the effect of the NWM seaport on the territorial attractiveness of the Oriental region. However, we were unable to measure its impact due to lack of sufficient data. Another limitation of this essay is related to the length of the interview, which was influenced by the pandemic situation (COVID 19). Therefore, one of the perspectives of this paper is to conduct an analysis of the effect of the NWM seaport on regional FDI flows using econometric models.

References

- (1) Alexandre Moine (2006). The territory as a complex system : an operational concept for planning and geography, geographic space, Tome 35, 117
- (2) Ali Kharroubi (2009). Oujda : l'Oriental peaufine son décollage économique' (Oujda: the Oriental Region refines its economic take-off)
- (3) BERD (2015). Projet Nador West Med, 1-35
- (4) Bertacchini Y (2002). Territoire et Territorialités. Vers l'intelligence territoriale, – volet 1-, Collection Les E.T.I.C (Ecrits des Technologies de l'information et de la Communication), 200.
- (5) Bruno Jean (2008). Territorial development : an emerging scientific discipline , communication presented within the framework of the conference of the Association for Regional Science of the French language
- (6) Coeuré B. & Rabaud I. (2003). Attractivité de la France : analyse, perception et mesure

- (7) Colletis G. and Rychen F. (2004). Companies and territories: proximity and local development, *Economy of proximity*. Hermès, 207-230
- (8) Culinane K et Wayne K.telley (2006). Port economics, research in transportation economics,16.
- (9) Di Méo G.(1999). Géographie sociale et territoires. In: *Annales de Géographie*, 608, 1999, 441.
- (10) El majidi et Lakhloufi (2017), *The Logistics Infrastructure at the Service of the Territorial Attractiveness: A comparative study Morocco-Nigeria-South Africa*, Book of proceedings, Tome II , 30-42
- (11) Fischer (1963). Les ports maritimes. Essai de classification, *L'Information Géographique*, 27 (3), 105-114
- (12) Francis K. & Régis LT (2009). Clusters, competitiveness poles and development poles: territorial and partnership dimension of innovation processes, governance and development attractiveness.
- (13) Goss, R. (1990). Economic Policies and Seaports: 1, The Economic Functions of Seaports, *Maritime Policy and Management*, 17(3), 207 – 219.
- (14) Goss, R. O. (2002). An early history of maritime economics. *International Journal of Maritime Economics*, 4 (4), 390-404.
- (15) Haezendonck, Elvira & Pison, Greet & Rousseeuw, Peter & Struyf, Anja. (2000). The Competitive Advantage of Seaports. *Maritime Economics and Logistics*. 2. 69-82.
- (16) Harvey (1989). From Managerialism to Entrepreneurialism: The Transformation in Urban Governance in Late Capitalism, *Human Geography*, 71 (1), 3-17.
- (17) Hasnaa GABER (2015). Marketing territorial : quels enseignements pour approcher la dynamique territoriale de la region de l'oriental, *Revue Marocaine de Recherche en Management et Marketing*,11, Janvier, 33-55.
- (18) Hatem (2004). Attractiveness what are we talking about? *Local Powers Review*, n ° 61
- (19) Hatem F. & L. Py (2008). Location Factors in the Activities Related to innovation of Multinationals: a Literature Review, OCDE
- (20) HCP (2017). *The Oriental Region: Figures and Analyses*, Oujda Regional Directorate.
- (21) Jackson G. (1983). *The history and archaeology of ports*. World's Workds Ltd., 176
- (22) James Bird's (1971). *Seaports and Seaport Terminals*, Hutchinson University Library, London, 75.
- (23) Lajarge R.(2000), Territorialité intentionnelles, des projets à la création des Parcs Naturels Régionaux (Chartreuse et Monts d'Ardèche), Thèse de Géographie, Univ. J. Fourier, Grenoble 1, 662
- (24) Lakhloufi et Moussamir (2020). Port logistics and economic growth: An empirical investigation of Morocco, *revue AME*, 2(3), 1-15.
- (25) LEADER (1999). La compétitivité territoriale : construire une stratégie de développement territoriale à la lumière de l'expérience.
- (26) Malecki (2004). Jockeying for position: what it means and why it matters to regional development policy when places compete, *Regional Studies*, 38, 1101-1120.
- (27) Ministry of Tourism Handicrafts and Social Economy (2009). Les potentialités écotouristiques dans la région de l'Oriental.
- (28) Mohamed MBARKI (2016). l'oriental : sociale par conviction, solidaire par culture, *Développement des Territoires de l'Oriental*, 2, 3-4.
- (29) Monios, Jason & Notteboom, Theo & Wilmsmeier, Gordon & Rodrigue, Jean-Paul. (2016). Competition and complementarity between seaports and hinterlands for locating distribution activities.
- (30) NWM (2014). *Resume de l'étude d'impact environnemental et social (EIES)*, 1-28
- (31) OECD (2005). *OECD Annual Report*

- (32) OECD (2011). Competition in Ports and Port Services, Policy round table, 1-327
- (33) Oujda Chamber of Commerce, Industry and Services (2016). Monograph of the Oriental Region.
- (34) P. Bauchet, (1992), Le transport maritime, Paris, Economica, 145, 1992
- (35) Park JS et Seo Y-J (2016) The impact of seaports on the regional economies in South Korea: panel evidence from the augmented Solow model. *Transport Res E-Log*, 85, 107–119
- (36) Prax. J. (2002). Le management territorial à l'ère des réseaux, éditions d'organisation, pp.22
- (37) Rietveld, P. (1989) Infrastructure and regional development, *Annals of Regional Science* 23(4), 255-274.
- (38) Rietveld, P., & Bruinsma, F. R. (1998). Is Transport Infrastructure Effective? *Transport Infrastructure and Accessibility; Impacts on the Space Economy*. Springer-Verlag.
- (39) Rodrigue, J.P. (1994). Transportation and spatial development in the Singapore extended metropolitan region, *Singapore Journal of Tropical Geography* 15(1): 56-74.
- (40) Sucháček, J (2008), Territorial marketing in the Czech Republic: a Trial-and-Error Process, Munich personal.
- (41) Thietart a.-c. & coll. (2003). *Méthodes de Recherche en Management*, Dunod, Paris
- (42) UMP (2015). Dossier with promotional documents: student guide, figures, annual report.
- (43) UNCTAD (1994). Port Marketing and the Challenge of the Third Generation Port. Trade and Development Board Committee on Shipping ad hoc Intergovernmental Group of Port Experts, TD / B / C.4 / AC.7 / 14, 13–23
- (44) UNCTAD (2011). Guide de l'investissement dans la région de l'Oriental du Maroc Opportunités et conditions, 1-108.
- (45) Vigarié (1993). Échanges et transports internationaux, Editions Dalloz - Sirey, Collection Mémentos de géographie Sirey.
- (46) Zheng, Shiyuan & Negenborn, R.R.. (2014). Centralization or decentralization: A comparative analysis of port regulation modes. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*.